

Policy implications for social innovation in forestry

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Over the last decade, the term Social Innovation (SI) has received increasing attention to address complex global social problems and to add collective values. The forest sector has many potentials for fostering employment, community development and for preventing land flight. It thus appears to be a promising field to investigate modes of SI in terms of collective action and collective benefits through both private and public-private collaborative efforts. One of the main advocates of the concept has formulated briefly that social innovation can be seen as ‘new ideas that address unmet social needs – and that work’ (Mulgan et al., 2007, p. 2). The paper focuses on examples for new “social practices” that have ultimately become institutionalized and asks the question of how new actors constellations and organizational innovations in forestry have led to innovative business solutions. Methodologically we examine this question with example of qualitative in-depth case studies in different European and Mediterranean countries and study how policies have impacted in fostering these innovations. In conclusion the paper derives the main factors for supportive policy and governance implications and provides an outlook for future governance of SI.